

Donor Properties of 1-amidino-O-alkylureas. Part XV. Tris(1-amidino-O-methylurea) Chromium(III) Complexes

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The preparation and properties of tris(1-amidino-O-methylurea) chromium(III) base and its nitrate and sulphate salts are described. The nitrate salt gives triunivalent electrolyte conductance in water. The electronic spectrum and magnetic moment are characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry. The 10 Dq value (20.4 kK) of the nitrate is comparable to that of tris(biguanide) chromium(III) chloride (20.7 kK).

EXTENSIVE studies have been made of 1-amidino-O-alkylureas as co-ordinating ligands with various transition metal ions such as copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II), cobalt(III), oxovanadium(IV), palladium(II) and zinc(II)¹. These studies have revealed a close similarity between biguanides and 1-amidino-O-alkylureas as ligands^{1,2}. We now report a study of the preparation and properties of chromium(III) complexes of 1-amidino-O-methylurea(I).

Experimental

1-Amidino-O-methylurea sulphate was prepared by published method³.

Tris(1-amidino-O-methylurea) chromium(III) base :

1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate (6 g) was dissolved in water (20 ml) by little warming and to the solution was added in portions under stirring chrome alum solution (2.5 g in 10 ml of water) with portion-wise addition of sodium hydroxide (3 g). The dark rose red coloured solution was cooled in ice (3 hr) when the complex tris(1-amidino-O-methylurea) chromium(III) base crystallised out. The compound was filtered through a sintered funnel and recrystallised from hot ethanol (60 ml) and dried in a desiccator over KOH (yield = 0.35 g). (Found : Cr, 13.0; N, 42.3 per cent. Calcd. for $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_3]$: Cr, 13.1; N, 42.3%).

Tris(1-amidino-O-methylurea) chromium(III) nitrate :

Tris(1-amidino-O-methylurea) chromium(III) base (0.35 g) was dissolved in a minimum volume of hot

alcohol (60 ml), concentrated (20 ml) and neutralised in the cold with dilute nitric acid. From the resulting solution light rose coloured complex was precipitated by the addition of acetone. The crystals were filtered, washed with acetone and dried in air (yield = 0.27 g). (Found : Cr, 9.1; N, 35.4%. Calc. for $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_3](\text{NO}_3)_3$: Cr, 8.9; N, 35.8%).

Tris(1-amidino-O-methylurea) chromium(III) sulphate :

The sulphate was obtained as above using dilute sulphuric acid instead of nitric acid, (yield = 0.3 g). (Found : Cr, 7.6; N, 25.3; SO_4^{2-} , 21.6; H_2O 18.9%. Calcd. for $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_3](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cr, 7.8; N, 25.0; SO_4^{2-} , 21.5; H_2O , 18.8%).

The compound loses the hydrated water only very slowly at 120°.

Magnetic moment : The susceptibility of the complex base was determined with the help of a Gouy balance at room temperature. Diamagnetic correction was made from Pascal's constants.

Found : $\chi_g = 14.52 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 5763 \times 10^{-6}$
 $\chi_{M(\text{corr})} = 5909.5 \times 10^{-6}$, $\mu = .377$ B.M.

Conductance : Conductance of 0.001M aqueous solution of the nitrate salt was determined at 25° with a Phillips Conductivity Bridge.

Results and Discussion

During the present investigation three compounds of chromium(III) with 1-amidino-O-methylurea as a ligand have been isolated. The base is rose red in colour and conforms to an anhydrobase, indicating that the ligand can behave as a monobasic acid. The corresponding biguanide complex base separated first as a monohydrate which could be dehydrated to an anhydrobase⁴. The base can be neutralised with H_2SO_4 or HNO_3 in alcohol to give the salts. Chloride and perchlorate salts were too soluble to be isolated. The molar conductance value of the complex nitrate (0.001M) in water (340 ohm⁻¹, cm², mole⁻¹ at 25°) indicates that it is a tri-univalent

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electrolyte⁵. The magnetic moment (3.77 B.M.) of the complex base is in accord with the expected spin only value for chromium(III) with three unpaired electrons⁶. The electronic spectrum of the nitrate salt in water gives bands at 490 nm (20.4 kK, $\epsilon = 86$) and at 370 nm (27.3 kK, $\epsilon = 62$). These two transitions can be assigned as ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and as ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$. The third transition ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ is in the ultraviolet. The first transition gives a 10 Dq value of 20.4 kK for the complex nitrate. This 10 Dq value is comparable to the 10 Dq (20.7 kK) of tris(biguanide) chromium(III) chloride⁷ and is little less than that (21.9 kK) of tris(ethylenediamine) chromium(III) chloride⁷. It is also interesting to note that the anhydrobase tris(1-amidino-O-methylurea) chromium(III) also gives two absorption bands at 20.0 kK and 25.9 kK. Thus the anhydrobase registers a slightly lower 10 Dq than the protonated nitrate salt. This must also be the case in the biguanide series since the chromium(III) complex base is crimson red while the salts are orange coloured⁸.

Attempts were made to obtain the chromium(III) complexes of 1-amidino-O-ethylurea. A dark red

solution of the complex base was obtained as for the 1-amidino-O-methylurea complex but no complex could be crystallised from solution presumably due to high solubility.

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